

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KUEK****FIRST NAME: SHERMAN****PROGRAM CODE: DRCTh****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 5****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Macbook

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the most important essence of a good academic essay?

- A lengthy essay with many facts from various sources.
- A paper that takes a substantial amount of time to write.
- A clear thesis statement with accompanying arguments.¹**
- An essay that has many challenging ideas found in it.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd edition (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

2. **Why is plagiarism considered an academic offence?**
- Because it involves stealing ideas that belong to other people.²**
 - Because it involves reading the writings of accomplished scholars.
 - Because it involves exchanging views with other people.
 - Because it involves quoting the words of other authors.
3. **When is it better to paraphrase than to quote an author?**
- When the author's ideas are exceptionally original.
 - When the author's ideas can be more clearly explained in your own words.³**
 - When the author's words strongly support your argument.
 - When the author's words greatly help to provide a clearer context for your discussion.
4. **What is the best solution when you find yourself overwhelmed by the complexity of your research project?**
- Divide the project into smaller parts and handle one manageable task at a time.⁴**
 - See the thesis supervisor to request for an immediate change of research topic.
 - Delegate the project to be taken over by students who are working under us.

² EUCLID, 5.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 32, 49.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 35.

- Visit an online forum to solicit advice from other people who are familiar with your topic.

5. **In the context of research, what is considered a good argument?**

- A good argument has an intimidating effect so that the reader does not dare challenge its statements.
- A good argument causes the reader to trust our statements because the reader knows us personally.
- A good argument offers good advice that has been passed down from one generation to another in our families.
- A good argument offers sound reasons and evidence that are worth being considered by the reader.⁵**

6. **What would be considered the most appropriate choice of words for academic writing?**

- Words that have the right meanings that the writer intends to communicate.⁶**
- Words that direct the reader's attention at other interesting topics.
- Words that are bombastic and impressive for the reader.
- Words that are demonstrate creativity in the writer's expression.

7. **What is the purpose of citation in academic writings?**

- To demonstrate a good example of how an academic dissertation should be written.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, 36.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 78.

- To ensure that your academic essay meets the stipulated length required by the course instructor.
 - To acknowledge the original work of other scholars and enable readers to pursue their own research.**⁷
 - To appreciate that the work undertaken by other scholars is worth being quoted in your essay.
8. **Based on the Chicago style, which of the following bibliographies is wrongly recorded?**
- Bruce Barron. *The Health and Wealth Gospel: What's Going on Today in a Movement that Has Shaped the Faith of Millions*. Illinois, 1987: InterVarsity Press.**⁸
 - Eco, Umberto. *How to Write a Thesis*. Translated by Caterina Mongiat Farina and Geoff Farina. Cambridge & London: The MIT Press, 2015.
 - Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
 - Vatikiotis, Michael. "Heavens, Asia's Going Christian". *Asia Times Online*. http://www.atimes.com/atimes/Southeast_Asia/HC2A.htm (accessed 15 September 2006).
9. **What is the main purpose of a literature review?**
- To demonstrate to the reader that the researcher has read well in the topic that is being researched.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 86.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 102.

- To emerge with credible arguments in support of the thesis statement that is advanced in the dissertation.
- To prevent the dissertation from being criticised by other scholars for having missed out one or two seminal readings.
- To emerge with a systematic update on the state of scholarship with regards to the matter which is being researched.⁹**

10. **How can you know when you are ready to embark on your proposed research?**

- When you are able to justify your research ideas and have planned your execution well.¹⁰**
- When you are able to think of a good title for the research and will be incorporating it into your proposal.
- When you are sure nobody else is researching the same topic and will be able to emerge with an original idea.
- When you have spoken with other scholars and obtained consensus that your research idea is a good one.

11. **How is qualitative research different from quantitative research?**

- Qualitative research deals with observation whereas quantitative research does only calculation.
- Qualitative research deals with non-measurable concepts whereas quantitative research deals with numerical data.¹¹**

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: Sage Publications, 2008), 46.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 17.

¹¹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 7, 8.

- Qualitative research involves writing in words whereas quantitative research does not involve the use of words.
- Qualitative research results in publishable reports whereas the reports generated from quantitative research cannot be published.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. California: Sage Publications, 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.